

Local reinforcement of thermoplastic polymers via robotically placed continuous fibre tow

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ABSTRACT

An integrated injection moulding process has been developed that combines the design freedom, cost efficiency, net-shape processing, and the existing infrastructure of injection moulding with robotically placed unidirectional (UD) thermoplastic composite yarns. Optimisation of the off-line tow placement process was performed and the mechanical properties and failure mechanisms studied. Increased tow placement rates increased porosity but actually also increased the UD tow tensile strength. Following the off-line tow placement process, the UD materials were warmed to facilitate interfacial healing during the over-moulding process. The UD materials, together with a metallic bush incorporated during tow placement, were placed in the over-injection moulding tool and over-moulded. UD tow inserts increased stiffness and strength by 60% to 118% and 62% to 202% for UD tow volume fractions of 18% and 36%. The over-moulding process reduced the UD tow porosity from typically 44% to 130%, for the two extremes of tow placement conditions.

Key words: Tow placement, injection moulding, hybrid process, local reinforcement, voids

1. INTRODUCTION

The injection moulding of thermoplastic polymers is an established processing method with a wide variety of applications produced for many industrial sectors. The process offers low cycle times and hence high manufacturing volumes from one tool to give net shaped components with low scrap rates resulting in a cost effective manufacturing route. Discontinuous random glass fibres have widely been added to increase the mechanical and thermal performance and such materials are used in many engineering applications. The ability to form highly complex geometries using the injection moulding process offers high product functionality and added value, and high component based stiffness. The main limitation of injection moulding is creep resistance for both plain polymer and short fibre reinforced materials. While short glass fibre reinforcement increases stiffness, high loading levels require large cross-sectional areas and load introduction becomes problematic.

An integrated moulding process has therefore been developed that combines the advantages of conventional injection moulding with the ability to locally place structural inserts of uni-directional (UD) glass or carbon fibres pre-impregnated with thermoplastic [1-2]. Load can hence be introduced into the component, the creep resistance improved, and the stiffness and strength increased, while working with the same or reduced cross-sectional areas. Design freedom is maintained with the flow-based injection moulding process, where the infrastructure of conventional injection moulding processing equipment and cycle times can be adopted. Structural properties can be achieved in regions of higher operating load by efficiently placed loops or ‘wire-frame’ inserts of UD materials, either via

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locally placed pultrusions or tailored geometries where a robotic system is used to place fibres *in-situ*. Use of the UD materials is limited and these are efficiently used, minimising material cost.

The objectives of this work were therefore to develop an integrated injection moulding process where UD tows of commingled glass and polypropylene (UD tow) are placed by robot in an off-line process before over-injection moulding. After reviewing the interfacial issues associated with integrated processing, a tow placement facility is described. With this facility and an over-injection moulding machine, the following aspects formed the focus of this investigation:

- effects of temperature and placement rate on placed tow properties before over-moulding;
- evaluation of the effect of tow placement conditions on properties after over-moulding;
- map the void content evolution in the UD tow through the process;
- study of the effect of relative percentage of UD fibres on tensile properties.

1.1 Integrated over-injection moulding

The integrated over-injection moulding process is shown schematically in Figure 1. The UD tow was placed off-line onto a metallic jig, with direct incorporation of metallic bushes to facilitate load introduction in the coupon. The UD tow, with embedded metallic bushes, was then heated to 160°C in a warming oven so that the over-injected material would heal to the UD tow. The placed UD tow was

not heated above the melt temperature (T_m), but warmed to optimise interfacial conditions and thereby maintain the integrity of the UD tow under flow forces. The warmed UD tow loop and integral bush were then transferred to the over-moulding tool. The UD tow was located at the centre line of the mould. The sample geometry studied is shown in Figure 2.

The interfaces of interest during this process, from an in-situ bonding perspective, are: between the UD-fibres during tow placement, and between the UD tow and over-moulded polymer during injection moulding. Following local surface rearrangement and intimate contact between the two surfaces, fusion bonding occurs as a result of inter-diffusion of polymer chains across the interface with re-crystallisation through the new interface completing bond formation during cooling [3]. Interfacial healing depends on pressure, temperature and heat conduction between the two surfaces, where the most important parameter is the average temperature of the two surfaces at the moment of contact. The focus during these experiments was to achieve, for the 2 interfaces, an average interfacial temperature above the polypropylene T_m at the moment of contact.

2. MATERIALS AND TESTING

2.1 Materials

The UD tow was a commingled yarn of glass (60 wt.%) and polypropylene fibres, supplied by Vetrotex International under the trade name Twintex™. The over-moulding material was a commercial homopolymer polypropylene grade with short glass fibre reinforcement (30 wt.%).

2.2 Mechanical testing and microscopy

Tensile tests were performed on UD tow loops before and after over moulding. All tests on UD tow loops (before over-moulding) used ‘pin-pin’ boundary conditions where steel pins were located in the metallic bushes to load the component (an extensometer was not used due to the tow geometry). Tests on the over-moulded samples, here using an extensometer to measure strain in the gauge length area, were performed in both pin-pin, and in a combined shear and pin loading condition (where the specimen was clamped in a custom fixture). Further details are given in the parallel paper [4].

Void content in the gauge length region was determined by optical microscopy where multiple images were taken of the entire cross section. The grey scale images were combined into a stack representing the sample area. A binary threshold was applied to this image to segment the porosity (black) from the reinforcing fibres and matrix material (white). The groupings of black pixels were then classified according to size and distribution using image analysis techniques. Crystallisation-based shrinkage voids in the over-moulded samples were filtered with an area-based morphological filter, with the size threshold the largest void area that occurred for each UD tow condition before over-moulding.

3. ROBOTIC TOW PLACEMENT TRIALS

3.1 Tow placement facility

A Stäubli®Unimation robot with 6 degrees of freedom was used to place the UD tow onto a metallic jig. The placement system consisted of a roller, a nozzle, and an air-cooling system, illustrated schematically in Figure 3 [5]. Here 5 UD tows were brought simultaneously into a heating tube before a final, independently controlled, heating nozzle, giving a tow temperature immediately before placement of 220°C. A metallic roller provided the consolidation force and directed the tow in the desired path. An air-cooling system was used to cool the tow after placement. This reduced deconsolidation effects and limited displacement of the previously placed material by tensile forces induced by tow placement occurring out of line immediately after placement of a previous section.

The UD tow was placed directly onto a temperature controlled metallic jig. The bushes were placed onto the metallic jig before the start of tow placement, such that they were partially embedded during the tow placement process.

The tow placement conditions were adapted from a previous study [5] where UD tows had been placed onto a polymer substrate. This study focussed on placing UD tow onto a heated metallic placement jig in order to: eliminate the production of the placement polymer preform, reduce potential warpage effects, potentially increase tow placement rates around curvature, and enable wrapping of UD tow around metallic bushes to improve load introduction. Hence, compaction pressure was applied by the roller in the straight regions, while the roller was retracted and UD material wrapped under tension around the bushes. Standard tow placement conditions used in this study, unless otherwise specified, were a placement rate of 100mm/s in the straight regions with an applied force of 80N (corresponding to a pressure of 32-46 bar, depending on the turn number [5]). A rate of 20mm/s was set for wrapping UD tow around the inserts (where the compaction roller was not used). This gave an effective cycle time of 62s for 4 turns, which was lower than the over-injection cycle time.

3.2 Temperature history during tow placement

The tow placement process requires the interfacial temperature between two subsequently deposited layers of tow to be above the polypropylene T_m of 165°C, requiring optimisation of the heated tube, nozzle, and placement jig temperatures, together with the air cooling stage. Based upon previous work, the heated tube and nozzle temperatures gave a tow temperature immediately before the compaction roller of 220°C [5].

3.2.1 Effect of placement jig temperature

Tow placement trials were made (4 turns of 5 yarns) where the placement jig temperature was varied between the minimum of 110°C and 130°C, at standard placement conditions. Mechanical tests were performed on the as placed UD tow (before over-moulding) with 'pin-pin' boundary conditions. A jig temperature of 130°C increased the tensile load to failure by 6% compared with 110°C, with a change in the failure mechanism from an 'unravelling' (interfacial failure) to simple fracture through the UD tow thickness, primary at the bush region. A temperature of 130°C was used for all further trials.

3.2.2 Effect of air cooling and mapping of thermal history

To gain an understanding of the interfacial conditions during deposition of successive layers of tow, thermocouples were used to record the UD tow temperature history during placement as a function of placement jig temperature and air-cooling level. A low placement rate of 20mm/s and an applied force

of 20N were used to enable placement of the thermocouples between successive tow layers. Figure 4 shows the thermal history with air-cooling where thermocouples were embedded between the jig and the first tow layer and then in-between subsequent tow layers as they were placed, at the same point along the tow. As the hot tow runs over the first thermocouple, the temperature initially rises to a peak (eclipsed by the limited thermocouple time constant) and then cools as the roller and then compressed air pass over the tow, controlling deconsolidation. The tow temperature then remains at the base plate temperature of 130°C. The robot continues to place the tow around the loop and a second thermocouple is inserted onto the first tow layer just before the robot passes over and deposits the second tow layer. Both the first thermocouple and the second thermocouple then show a temperature rise due to the high temperature of the placed tow before the temperature then drops due to the roller and the cooling air. The two tow layers then slowly increase in temperature towards the jig temperature. As subsequent tows are placed, the same sequence occurs, but with the temperature difference between the metallic base plate and the tow increasing, due to the insulating effect of the previously placed tows. This can limit the number of tow layers placed, unless additional substrate heating is applied. In practice, the number of turns should be controlled to minimised cycle times.

When air-cooling was not used, the tow produced was not usable due to deconsolidation resulting from the lack of cooling. Air-cooling had the effect of freezing the polypropylene just after pressure is applied thus controlling deconsolidation.

3.3 Placement conditions vs. quality of UD tow

Having optimised the interfacial healing conditions by studying the jig temperature and cooling method, the effect of placement speed and consolidation pressure in the linear regions at low and high levels was studied (Table 1: 6 samples for each the conditions) to investigate how UD tow loop properties were affected (before over-moulding). Tensile stress versus strain curves showed initial non-linear stress-strain behaviour at low strain levels, attributed to onset effects where the UD tows were 'straightening out'. This was followed by a generally linear behaviour. Table 1 shows that the tows deposited at high speed had an increased breaking load, with a limited effect of pressure (within the S.D.). A high consolidation pressure reduced the maximum force by 15% for low speed trials.

Table 1 Results of the UD tow tensile tests (before over-moulding)

Code/turns		Placement condition		σ_{max} (MPa)		E_s (GPa)		F_{max} (kN)		Void content, %
		Speed in straight line, V_s (mm/s)	Consolidation force, F (N)	mean	S.D.	mean	S.D.	mean	S.D.	
A	4	20	20	430 ±26		18.5 ±0.1		25.8 ±1.5		2.3
B	4	20	80	367 ±32		17.8 ±0.3		22.0 ±1.9		2.6
C	4	100	20	478 ±45		19.5 ±0.3		28.7 ±2.7		4.3
D	4	100	80	495 ±29		19.6 ±0.1		29.7 ±1.7		8.3
D	6			421 ±17		17.6 ±0.1		39.4 ±1.6		4.8
D	8			355 ±21		16.2 ±0.3		43.8 ±2.6		6.8

3.3.1 Effect of placement rate and consolidation pressure on microstructure

Micrographs were taken at the four conditions to examine the effect of placement conditions on consolidation quality (Figure 5). Increased porosities (4.3% to 8.3%) were evident in the tows deposited at high speed (which showed the highest tensile test results), compared with levels of 2.3 to 2.6% at low speed (Figure 6). Increased pressure did not significantly affect intra-bundle porosity. At low placement rates with low pressure, each layer of tow could be distinguished, with polymer rich regions between layers. Conversely, tows deposited at high speed showed increased porosity. Tows deposited at low speed had constant sections along the linear regions compared with tows deposited at high speed.

A hypothesis to explain why higher placement rates increased tow properties would be that: higher rates increased the tension in the tow during placement. The tension in the system (at processing

temperature) was measured to be 34 ± 3 N at 100mm/s. Hence fibres placed at higher rates would remain straighter, and closer to the tangents joining the bush internal diameters, than the tows deposited at low speed. Therefore, during the tensile test, the fibres do not need to realign before carrying the load. For the tows deposited at low speed, any realignment of the tow as the load is applied could cause the premature fracture. However, the same number of UD glass fibres are present in the sample independent of the UD tow porosity. Uniaxial loading, here measured as a force, will be less sensitive to porosity than the flexural

tests used previously [5] to study the effects of porosity on tow stiffness. For condition 'D', the UD tow loop tensile strength was within 11% of the material suppliers published data, with this reduction caused by stress concentrations at the metallic bushes.

3.3.2 Effect of number of UD tow turns on mechanical properties

Based upon the setting 'D', which gave the high placement rates necessary for economic production, and a high placement pressure (marginally increasing consolidation quality), the number of turns placed was varied from 4 to 8 (with 5 yarns per turn). This gave a range of 20 to 40 commingled yarns per UD tow loop and effective commingled yarn volume fractions in the over-moulded sample gauge length of 18% to 36%. A 48% increase in maximum force between sample D4 and D8 occurred in the as placed samples (before over-moulding), as shown in Table 1.

4. OVER-INJECTION MOULDING TRIALS

4.1 Tooling

The objective of the over-moulding process was to embed the UD tow insert with both bushes in a polypropylene matrix, to obtain a generic coupon for testing. The UD tow insert was located at the part centre line in the over-injection moulding tool.

4.2 Equipment and over-moulding cycle

The over-moulding process was performed at the DaimlerChrysler research centre (Ulm, Germany) on a Krauss Maffei injection machine, equipped with a hydraulic clamping unit. The over-injection parameters used were: mould temperatures of 50°C, injection temperature of 260°C, packing pressure of 500 bar, holding time of 10s, cooling time of 90s, giving a total in-mould cycle time of 100s. An example of the generic coupon produced, here shown with an unreinforced and hence transparent PP grade, is shown in Figure 7. All over-moulding trials for mechanical tests were performed with a 30 wt.% short glass fibre PP grade. The following steps were performed:

- i) preheat the UD tow insert, with integral metallic bushes, to 160°C
- ii) rapid transfer (<10s) of (warmed) UD tow into the over-injection moulding tool (bushes are located on guide pins)
- iii) injection moulding tool is closed and the UD tow position fixed in the tool centre

iv) over-injection of polymer melt

4.3 Mechanical testing of over-injected samples

In order to gain an initial understanding of the effects of UD inserts on mechanical properties, and of the effect of tow placement conditions on UD coupon properties after over-moulding, a series of samples were produced. All tensile tests were conducted using a MTS tensile machine with a 100 kN load cell. Two principal test boundary conditions were studied: pin-pin loading and a combined shear-pin loading configuration, which are described in the parallel paper [4]. For the latter, strain was measured with a 135 mm gauge-length extensometer. The tensile modulus was determined from the slope of the stress-strain curves in the strain interval 0.05% - 0.25%. Tensile tests were performed on the plain short GF/PP specimens, the four tow placement test conditions, and for over-moulded 6 and 8-turn coupons, with a series of five samples per coupon or test type [4].

4.3.1 Pin-pin loading: – effect of tow placement conditions (4-turns)

Samples with 4 turns of UD tow had an average commingled yarn volume fraction of 18%. Under pin-pin loading conditions (as used for the UD tow insert tensile tests), failure initiated with fracture of the over-moulded polymer at the weld line, leading to a drop in force. The UD tow insert continued to support the load until final fracture occurred. Failure in the pin-pin load introduction cases was caused by stress concentrations at the bush region. The results for samples over-moulded with the four tow placement conditions (Table 2) showed that, within the range of tow placement conditions studied, the over-moulding process reduced the property range of the different tows. A 35% difference existed before over-moulding, which was reduced to 11% after over-moulding. However, high placement rates still showed marginally higher properties after over-moulding. Tows deposited at low speed, with high consolidation force, showed the lowest results. Comparison of the plain GF/PP samples with the UD insert reinforced samples showed a 130% increase in breaking force.

Table 2 Effect of UD tow placement conditions on properties after over-moulding (pin-pin fixture)

Placement condition			F_{max} (kN)	
turns	placement F.	placement V.	mean	S.D.
None, plain PP (30% W_f glass)			15.2 \pm 0.2	
A4	20	20	34.2 \pm 0.7	
B4	80	20	32.3 \pm 1.2	
C4	20	100	35.2 \pm 0.7	
D4	80	100	35.8 \pm 0.3	

4.3.2 Combined pin-shear loading: – effect of tow placement conditions (4-turns)

In this test configuration samples were loaded with a shear fixture and pins, as detailed in the parallel paper [4]. As before, samples with 4 turns of UD tow had an average commingled yarn volume fraction of 18%. As can be seen in Table 3, the 4 sets of tow placement conditions did not significantly effect the tensile modulus and strength.

Table 3 Effect of number of UD tow turns on properties after over-moulding (pin-shear fixture)

Placement condition			F_{max} (kN)		E, (GPa)		σ_{max} , (MPa)		Void content, %	
code	placement F.	placement V.	mean	S.D.	mean	S.D.	mean	S.D.	total	filtered
none			22.3		6.3 ± 0.25		75.6 ± 2.1			
A4	20	20	36.6		9.8 ± 0.39		124.0 ± 2.4		1.8	1.6
B4	80	20	36.9		9.7 ± 0.41		125.0 ± 6.1		3.9	2.1
C4	20	100	36.8		9.7 ± 0.50		124.6 ± 9.0		5.1	1.1
D4	80	100	36.2		10.1 ± 0.38		122.5 ± 3.7		4.9	3.6
D6			55.0		11.6 ± 0.33		186.2 ± 13.9		8.2	4.9
D8			67.5		13.7 ± 0.47		228.4 ± 21.9		11.8	5.8

4.3.3 Combined pin-shear loading: – effect of tow content

In order to further increase the mechanical properties, UD tow inserts were produced with 6 turns and 8 turns of UD tow to give (after over-moulding) average commingled yarn volume fractions of 27% and 36% respectively. As seen in Table 3, tensile modulus and strength increased with increasing tow content. These coupons failed primarily in the gauge length section, or at the thickness reduction. Hence weld-line failure was not observed to be the dominating failure mode.

4.4 Effect of over-moulding on porosity

The over-moulding process was found to generally reduce void content for all of the tow placement conditions, with the exception of the growth of a few large area voids during over-moulding (Figures 6, 8, and 9), considered to occur from local crystallisation shrinkage. These were filtered using image analysis techniques where any void in the over-moulded sample that was greater in area than the largest void area in the as placed tow was removed. Figure 9 shows the void area size distribution for the four tow placement conditions before and after over-moulding. Hence the numbers of smaller matrix-based and intra-bundular voids, of an effective diameter (converted to a circle) less than 120µm, were reduced during the over-moulding process, as shown in Figure 8. This is considered a mechanical collapsing process due to the ductile behaviour of the UD tow (preheated to 160°C) together with dissolution of the trapped gas into the matrix. Porosity levels were reduced from 1.8% to 1.6% and 11.8% to 5.8% for the highest and lowest initial void contents (A4 and D8).

5. CONCLUSIONS

A hybrid moulding process has been developed that combines robotic tow placement with over-injection moulding. Tow placement parameters were optimised and air-cooling was needed to control deconsolidation. Increased tow placement rates increased tensile properties but also increased porosity. At a placement rate of 100mm/s, the inserts were produced in an off-line process in under 62s. Over-injection moulding was performed in a standard cycle, with the UD tow located at the part centre line. For ‘pin-pin’ test conditions, UD insert reinforced samples (4-turns) showed a 130% increase in breaking force compared with a standard injection moulded coupon (30wt.% short glass filled), showing the ability of UD tows to introduce load into structures. For combined ‘pin-shear’ test conditions, UD tow inserts increased stiffness and strength by 60% to 118% and 62% to 202% for UD tow volume fractions of 18% and 36% (4 and 8 turns), compared with the reference specimen.

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